

FABRICATION OF SOFT COMPOSITE FLAPPING ACTUATOR

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ABSTRACT

Fabrication of a flapping actuator entails a few possible materials such as shape memory alloy (SMA), ionic polymer-metal composite, and piezo-ceramic material. In this research, SMA wires were embedded into the soft composite actuator as the main source of flapping motion. In order to build the flapping actuator capable of high-frequency motion, a soft composite was fabricated, integrating mainly 3 components: SMA wires as the actuating source, 3D printed scaffolds as a control matrix for the SMA wires which together create intended motion, and PDMS as a binder to hold all the parts as one solid piece. The flapping mechanism is basically induced from the division of the SMA wires into two groups on each side making it possible for the whole actuator to move up and down when electricity is alternatively applied to each set of SMA wires, it resulted in the maximum lifting force of 0.1 N at 4 Hz actuation speed, which opened up the possibility of fabricating flying actuators made of soft composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since humanity invented an electric motor and a jet engine, a variety of flying vehicles have been developed manufactured, and serviced to the needs of the society and its people. Along with the development of such mechanical aero-crafts, scientists and researchers also have been making attempts to create a biomimetic flying machine such as an ornithopter which flies by flapping its wings. Yet, the artificial flying mechanism human made is high-energy consuming, heavy, and lacks agility. These demerits stem from using mechanical components such as a gear, joint, nut, and parts made of metals in assembling aero-crafts.

To overcome the limitations and the flaws of the conventional aero-crafts' flying mechanism, many research on utilizing 'smart materials' to achieve biomimicry have been carried out. A few substances considered smart materials and most frequently used among them are 'shape memory alloy (SMA)', 'ionic polymer metal composite (IPMC)', and 'lead zirconate titanate (PZT)'. Each of the listed materials, in combinations of other substances, displays specific activation traits of movement. According to the previous works in related studies, while 'IPMC' and 'PZT' are capable of relatively high actuation – that is moving repeatedly within the maximum tip points, 'SMA' is denoted for its low actuation speed. Conversely, SMA-based actuators generate stronger force while 'IPMC' and 'PZT' could not, as much as SMA does. Table 1 shows the trait specifications of the various type of actuators made of the aforementioned smart materials, 'SMA', 'IPMC', 'PZT' For such reasons, the application and functionality of the actuators fabricated from the academia are quite distinct and differ from one another classified by the type of smart materials on which each actuator was based.

To give a few examples, 'IPMC'-based robots take the biomimetic form of a jellyfish, fish, and mostly underwater creatures; IPMC displays a trait of high deformation with a relatively weak level of force [4, 5]. For the case of PZT-based biomimetic robots, Wyss Institute at Harvard successfully created a mini flying robot using PZT, named 'RoboBees' in 2013 [6]. Now, the applications of SMA materials in crafting a biomimetic robot include the ones such as a turtle, flea, fish and underwater

creatures again [1, 2, 3, 7, 8]. Similarly, SMA based robots have been used in underwater environments as well; this seems to be due to the available cooling advantages of the water for the heated SMA wires actuated for the movement of the robots. Yet, if there were some differentiation with the other two applications of the listed smart materials, because of the SMA's capability of generating stronger force, it is used in building small biomimetic robots. As examples, a SMA spring actuated robot having the size of 2.2 x 2.7 x 1.2 mm and a water strider robot with the size of 100 x 80 μm were developed [9,10]. The water strider robot, in particular, makes use of the TRC (Torque Reversal Catapult) mechanism copied from the jumping motion of a flea. As can be seen from these robots, SMA, by conventional scholars, is characterized with strong force generation, slow actuations, and good deformations.

	SMA	IPMC	PZT
Deformation	High	High	Low
Actuation Speed	Low	High	High
Force Generation	High	Low	Low

Table 1. Traits of the most commonly used smart materials

What's more, the performance of the actuators of these smart materials, especially SMA, was greatly improved by the usage of 'SSC', the acronym for 'Smart Soft Composite' actuators [11]. This actuator enhanced the simple, limited motion of former smart material based actuators, by integrating a scaffold, SMA wires, and PDMS (polydimethylsiloxane). Especially, according to a specific pattern or structure of the scaffold, a complex motion could be manifested, in combinations of SMA wires, without any motors or mechanical structures. Using the SSC actuator, there has been a research which achieved the SMA actuating speed of 35 Hz [2]. However, this high-frequency SMA-based actuator realized the fast frequency not in twisting but in bending direction. In this context, within this research, the purpose is to fabricate a biomimetic, flapper based on SMA wires in the form of SSC actuator capable of creating fast bending and twisting actuation simultaneously. More detailed objectives would include 1) achievement of SMA based, high-frequency actuator and 2) generating positive lift force by the actuator.

2 ACTUATOR DESIGN & FABRICATION

The flapping actuator comprises of SMA wires, scaffolds, and PDMS whose functionalities within the solid body differ. While SMA wires are the sources of the flapping motion, the scaffold renders stiffness to the body and creates twisting and bending trajectory of the actuators along with the contraction-expansion motion of the SMA wires. PDMS encapsulates the scaffold and the SMA wires together as a solid piece. The dimension of the PDMS would also have an impact on the stiffness of the actuator.

The scaffold design is quite important in that according to the different patterns and layer structures, the behavior of the flapping would totally change. The patterns of scaffold parts could be drawn from any CAD programs and be printed into a physical product. In this research, the flapping actuator has the scaffold embedded inside, sandwiched up and down by the two sets of SMA wires. The role of the scaffold within this type of actuator is to create a flapping motion that entails both bending and twisting movement. Especially, if the flapping actuators were to fly, there needs to be a total positive sum of lift force generated upon a few flapping movements by the actuators. For this reason, the flapping up and down movement of the actuator requires different trajectory of motion and that means it is necessary either to reduce the drag force for the flapping-up movement or to increase the lifting force generated by the flapping-down movement. This could be achieved by configuring different

patterns in each layer of the scaffold embedded in the flapping actuator.

Three layers of different patterns make up the scaffold structures, shown in Figure 1. Having the 2nd layer in the middle, the patterns of the other layers up and down are not identical but cross each other in geometry. With its third layer facing upward and the first layer placed at the bottom, each of them controls the movement behavior of the flapping-up and flapping-down movement, respectively. The mechanism behind this is the interaction between the pattern of the scaffold and SMA wires' contraction and expansion movement when actuated. In Figure 1, the angles between the pattern of each layer and the deformation direction of the SMA wires are indicated; the angle configuration is 45/0/90°. Since each set of SMA wires are placed above and below the scaffolds, the behavior of the flapping-up movement is most strongly affected by the interaction with the 3rd layer and that of the flapping-down movement is highly influenced by the presence of the 1st layer structure.

Figure 1. Configuration of the scaffold

As the pattern of the bottom layer crosses with the bottom set of SMA wires perpendicularly, during the flapping-down movement of the actuator, the generated force by the SMA wires is almost evenly distributed throughout the actuator, resulting in simple bending motion. However, for the flapping-up movement, the generated force is asymmetrically delivered to the body, owing to the difference in the stiffness of the 3rd layer in x-direction and y-direction, which as a consequence, results in the twisting and bending motion of the actuator, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Behavior of the actuators moving up and down

The fabrication process of the flapping actuator is indicated in Figure 3. It first starts with the usage of a 3D printer to manufacture 1) a scaffold and 2) a mold which gives a physical form of the actuator with PDMS. The specific name of the scaffold and the mold materials used for the actuator is ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene). Once, the parts are printed out, the three components which are the

scaffold, SMA wires, and PDMS are integrated. As can be seen in step 2 and 3 in Figure 3, two sets of SMA wires are placed above and below the plane of the scaffold, being fixated on the mold. Then, the PDMS is poured into the mold and cured in the furnace for a few hours. These processes complete the solidification of the actuator to have a tangible form. The next step entails wiring and clamping of the SMA wires, which is essential for the electric control of the actuator. After all these steps, a solid, complete flapping actuator is made.

Figure 3. Fabrication of the flapping actuator

The actual image of the fabricated actuator is shown below in Figure 4. In order to make it a bird-wing-like structure and to test the lift force of the actuator, a wing frame made of Polyvinyl was attached to the actuator, after the fabrication.

Figure 4. Flapping actuator with its polyvinyl wing

3 EXPERIMENT & RESULT

The mechanism to trigger the flapping movement of the actuator is through the alternative heating of each set of SMA wires inside the actuator. One cycle of the flapping motions is achieved when first, the upper set of SMA wires are heated by the electric current inducing the twisting and bending motion and then the lower set of SMA wires are also heated by the current causing the flapping-down motion. Basically, it is the contraction-expansion cycle of the SMA wires heated by the electric current that makes the actuator move in interaction with the scaffold's layer pattern. The quality of the flapping performances of the actuator was assessed mainly by two measurements: 1) angular deformation of the actuator's movement up and down and 2) the lift force generated. The conditions for these two experiments share the voltage and current value of 6 V and 1.5 A, respectively.

First, the assessment of bending and twisting deformation of the flapping motion was carried out. One of the ends of the actuator was fixed to the gripper and then its flapping motion was triggered by conducting electricity to each set of SMA wires alternatively. For the measurement of its performance, the maximum tip angle of the flapping motion up and down was considered. The value of the maximum angle turned out to be about 32° for the bending motion and 25° for the twisting motion, shown in Figure 5-2. Within the figure, the reference line indicates the starting position of the flapping actuator. It could be questioned why the angle was taken from the reference line, instead of the maximum downward position induced by the flapping down movement. This is simply because the maximum downward position happens to be near the reference line.

Figure 5-1. Maximum bending angle of the flapping motion

Figure 5-2. Maximum twisting angle of the flapping motion

Next, the lifting force of the flapping actuator was measured using a dynamometer (KISTLER). The flapping actuator was fixed onto the gripper placed on the dynamometer and the force created by the flapping movements were calculated through the Matlab Program. The experiment as shown in Figure 6 was set up in ways the force generation in the X direction indicates the lift power of the actuator and the one measured in Y direction indicates its thrust.

Figure 6. Set up for the flapping force measurement

The result is shown in Figure 7. For the testing, the frequency of the actuator was 4 Hz and therefore made 4 cycles up and down in one second. In the graph, the force measured stayed approximately 0 until 2.5 seconds and after the actuation, the force was calculated and then visualized. It shows the force generated in the X direction; there exists positive upward force and negative downward force during one second of its actuation period. To calculate the lift force of the flapping actuator in one cycle, which in this case was recorded in the X direction, the difference between the maximum upward force and the maximum downward force was taken into consideration. The value of the difference between them is about 0.025 N; it could be interpreted that per one cycle of flapping up and down motion, 0.025 N was created. Additionally, because there were 4 cycles in one second, the force generated in one period of second during the actuation is four times bigger than the difference value, which happens to be about 0.1 N.

Figure 7. Force generated in one cycle in the X and Y direction

Aside from the force gauged in the *X* direction, the one in the *Y* direction was as well measured. This force value corresponds to the thrust toward the position of the gripper where the end of the actuator was fixed. The desired motion of the actuator is the movement of flapping and flying. If the actuator, however, was to be used as a biomimetic fin of a robotic fish, it would definitely create thrust needed to propel the body of the robot forward. In the second graph of Figure 7, the thrust value was calculated from the difference between the maximum upward force and the maximum downward force. Per one cycle of flapping up and down motion, the total net force of 0.15 N was produced. Again, because there were 4 cycles of force generation in one second, the amount of thrust force in one second is about 0.6 N. Yet, if the actuator was connected to the body of a bird robot, the force in the *Y* direction would be directed toward the inner side of the body, which would not play a significant role in making it fly. The summary of the actuator's flapping performances is given in Table 2. Here, the lift force measured does not directly indicates whether or not it is able to fly because the weight and the drag factor need to be considered at the same. In this context, future works would include the calculation of the lift to drag ratio which identifies its capability of actually flying.

Flapping Actuator at 4 Hz		
Size (mm) & Mass (g)	100 x 30 mm	16 g
Voltage (V) & Current (A)	6 V	1.5 A
Bending Angle (°)	32 °	
Twisting Angle (°)	25 °	
Force (N) : <i>X</i> -Direction	0.1 N (max)	
Force (N) : <i>Y</i> -Direction	0.6 N (max)	

Table 2. Results of the flapping performances

5 CONCLUSION

The fabrication process for making the flapping actuator has been developed within the research. Overall, the actuator based on those process resulted in the maximum lift force of 0.1 N, making flapping motions at the bending and twisting angle of 32° and 25° at 4 Hz actuation speed, which hinted for possibility of fabricating actual flying actuators made of soft composite. Its contribution lies in the design of the scaffold pattern inside the flapping actuator. Owing to the asymmetrical structure of the scaffold, the actuator is capable of creating lift force. The measured lift force per one cycle was 0.015 N. If the flapping frequency of the actuator is fast enough, force generation will be greatly improved, having the multiples of 0.015 N by the number of strokes made within one second. Though the lift force was not big enough to make the actuator fly, artificially causing the actuator to do the bending and twisting motion at 4 Hz, as a form of biomimicry was meaningful

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